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PROJECT TITLE: Planning with youth: a tool and a framework for an engaging, meaningful and forward-looking participation of youngsters in shaping attractive and sustainable living environments.

WP3: Testing alternative participatory tools

Activity: Exploring with multimodal interaction for the engagement of youth in the context of spatial planning: city sound and soundscapes.

“The sound of places” (sv. Platsens ljud)

Summary of the event on sound and spatial planning:

Event held on 1st December 2021
at Flemingsberg, Sweden

Funder:	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development - FORMAS
Project ID:	2019-01887
Lead partner:	Södertörn University, Department for Environment, Development and Sustainability Studies, Sweden
Participating project partner:	KTH - School of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science
Coordinating researchers:	Romina Rodela, Sofia Lundmark, Maurizio Goia

Summary

The research project **Planning with Youth** is a study of participatory spatial planning with special interest in methods for the engagement of youth in participatory spatial planning. As part to Work Package 3 we explore with novel tools and methods, and in that context are interested in the potential of **multimodal interaction** for opening up new opportunities for younger demographic groups to engage in planning. Questions related to how and why multimodal interaction holds potential for planning and place making, with special interest for the role of soundscapes, we raised at a gathering of practitioners, researchers and artists organized on December 1st 2021 by the Department of External Relations at Södertörn University. The event had a special focus on the development of the residential area of Flemingsberg and the discussions that emerged in that context are summarised in this activity report.

Key words: multimodal interaction, smart city, Flemingsberg, planning with youth, residential development, sound, soundscapes.

Planning with Youth research project updates can be followed at these platforms:

YouTube Channel: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCsHIGTxPzi98A1yeDJR37g>

Project blogging site: <https://medium.com/youth-plan>

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1. Introduction

Participatory spatial planning of urban areas is concerned with inclusion of local residents on matters that affect their living environments, and as part to this it is expected that planners reach out and allow for local residents, citizens and their representatives to access information and express their needs and views on upcoming developments, or other change in their areas. While participatory processes are valued and regarded as a very important democratic tool which helps to fostering thriving local communities, it is well documented how such processes are better able to attract some social groups more than others. For instance, literature has already documented how some participatory processes may often fail to reach out, and attract, the participation of younger demographic groups and as a consequence their needs, values and preferences, relating to urban areas where they live, remain poorly understood and less integrated into spatial planning when compared to older demographic groups.

It is documented that the most widely used tools and methods for participatory processes are perceived as out of touch with younger demographic groups and many are now suggesting for the need to explore and innovate on how we do and run participatory process. In the research project **Planning with Youth** we experiment with novel methods and as part to this are interested in the potential of **multimodal interaction** with special interest for how, when and the ways in which *visual*, and *auditive* information about the urban environment might open up new opportunities for younger demographic groups to engage in planning. On December 1st 2021 the Department of External Relations at Södertörn University organized a workshop titled “**The Sound of Places**” (sv. Platsens ljud) where our project team co-hosted activities alongside the performance collective, and artist-in residence, Johanssons pelargoner och dans¹. The core objective of the workshop was to discuss the role of planning and place making from a more creative viewpoint, informed by artistic and creative means. The event activities have centred on the current plans for the development of the residential area of Flemingsberg in the municipality of Huddinge. The visiting artists delivered an audio walk in the nature and playgrounds serving the housing district nearby the Flemingsberg train station. Our project team delivered a facilitated discussion and the help of our project partner – KTH, have given a demonstration. The outcomes of the discussion session are summarized in the following after the positioning of multimodal interaction in the context of participatory planning centred on children and youth.

2. The potential of multi-modal interaction and the use of sound

The research and practice concerned with the engagement of children and youth in spatial planning assumes that some of that failures can be ascribed to inadequate tools and methods used as part to participatory process. For instance, workshops, large gatherings, or other expert meetings where important information, facts, numbers and maps are shared, and used to inform the discussion. However, research suggests that some of these formats fail to attract children and youth who might not see these processes, and the information shared there, as relevant, salient, and meaningful for them. Children and youth are not experts and do not see themselves as such, they might not feel very comfortable when asked to engage with, comment on, and discuss bits and pieces of data which they do not feel familiar with, or do not really understand. In the research project **Planning with Youth** we aim to study the potential and use of alternative methods for youth participation. This inclusive of methods that give space for playfulness, creativity, and expression under the assumption that in so doing planners and practitioners may create better opportunities for inclusion, and youth participation, and for youth to more easily find their voice to express preferences, experiences, values,

¹ <https://www.pelargonerochdans.se/>

and needs they have in relation to their environment where they live. In the research project **Planning with Youth** we study the potential of games used for serious purposes, of participatory mapping and creative crafting in planning, and also are interested to explore the potential of multimodal interaction in this regard.

With the increasing uptake of technological advancements *at the level of the individual city dweller* (e.g. access to smart phone technology and Internet) across a wide span of age groups inclusive of young adults, teenagers and pre-teens, and at the *level of city council administration* (e.g. diffusion of sensors in cities to gather data about) holds promise for participatory spatial planning. Specifically, the use of technological devices (e.g. smartphone, microphone, camera, display, keyboard, mouse, pen, track ball, data glove, virtual reality headset) to gather, share, understand, and communicate *visual, auditive, and tactile* information in reference to the urban environment might open up new opportunities for younger demographic groups to engage in new ways in participatory spatial planning. In the research project **Planning with Youth** we are interested to study and explore the potential of multimodal interaction and specifically focusing on sound and video.

3. Outcomes from the discussions

The workshop facilitated by our team consisted of about 11 participants to include professionals employed by Huddinge municipality and the Stockholm region, local area developers, but also researchers and artists. The activity was divided in three parts. During a first part the participants were invited to reflect and annotate their views, opinions, and experiences on current situation, possibilities, and challenges in relation to the role of sound and planning. During the second part we have asked participants to work in small groups and consider possible ideas for micro project under this topic that could be of interest for Flemingsberg residential area. The last activity consisted of a practical demonstration given by our project partner – KTH of multimodal interaction. A small device (a wireless inertial measurement unit) fitted on a strap-on was prepared for the demonstration. Participants could wear it on their hand and thereby experience how to generate and modify sounds of the city in real time by means of simple body gestures.

3.1 Challenges and opportunities for the use of sound / soundscapes in relation to participatory processes in residential area development

During the first part participants were invited to express opinions on current challenges and opportunities of the use of sound in residential area development, and also promoted visions for the future. Participants posted individual notes on three separate posters each about a different topic: current situation, possibilities, and challenges. A summary of the feedback received is annotated here:

Current situation:

- Eg. dance floor-bluetooth enables spontaneous use of a place
- Sound as security-creating (calming) of a place
- Sounds that bring life to a place by offering artistic experiences
- Sound in headphones
- Composer
- Activate hearing and vision on the site(s) through works with sound and instructions
- Art, the power of the voice, instructions
- Develop sound concepts that correspond to the theme, theory and method of performing arts projects
- Choreography
- Sound design for performing arts
- Work artistically, use sound and music to create worlds in art
- Sound today is not a special area within cooperation - but gets energy from it

- Not so much, when it comes to site development, classical music, security, and safety
- Create sounds: water, music, gravel, wind chimes
- Mute sound: soft surfaces, rules, nets, noise barrier
- Investigate laws: noise investigation, noise requirements
- Dance collective, archaeologist and works with a nature trail and audio tracks
- Dance floor! Where it is possible to connect your own sound and dance
- Floor plan: quiet zones, social zones, etc.
- Well-being based (common areas)
- Principal of The Stockholm University College of Music Education (SMI): designed SMI's premises (acoustics, sound- and work environment, etc.)
- Technically proficient in PA technology for music performances
- Choir- and orchestra conductor (musician): performs in different sound environments, indoors and outdoors
- Laws and regulations (work environment)
- Noise investigations: legal requirements regarding noise level, sources of noise/sound, solutions for good sound environments
- Investigates noise levels in detailed plans to create good future sound environments, investigates sources of noise, develops physical solutions to minimize noise
- Create rooms with sound
- Create dynamics, dramaturgy in music
- Voice (speech) in performing arts, address, and tone, etc.
- Works with soundscapes in participant-based performing arts
- Bilateral sound
- Music and dance

Possibilities:

- Opportunity to change the experience of a place + create new experiences
- Create participation with a place in the planning and in the finished site by changing the sound
- Analyze sound images in planned environments more varied
- Digitization
- Work to amplify certain sounds - not just mute, remove
- Create security/insecurity
- An underestimated mind. Large white spots regarding what sound can be.
- Sound for privacy and intimacy, as well as for community
- Sound focus to influence other development
- Good in the present: a chance to be introverted, and listen - inward
- Can provide new perspectives
- Help to come down in your own body
- Help to come down in a place
- Create emotions and moods
- Create new sound environments in creative ways in exposed situations
- Interaction: residents/those operating in a place, activating, integrating
- Interaction of citizens in the planning process - dialogue and views
- "compose" in harsh environments with muffled sounds
- Inform, spark interest
- Create an experience
- Increased well-being
- Increased focus
- Pay attention to qualities in a place

- Re-create places/experience of places
- Increase the well-being of individuals
- Put the imagination in motion
- Working integrated: artistically interdisciplinary, different participant perspectives, experience-based, composed, improvised
- Work with sound and sound creation as a gate to music and music creation
- Sounds that can evoke a feeling
- Sound to make a place safe
- Sounds that make us aware of our own body and other bodies
- Sounds that can scare people away from a place
- Sound to have your voice heard
- Evokes emotions
- Creates moods
- Available via headphones
- A dimension for memories and stories (collected at museums)
- Growing interest, ASMR, etc.
- Must have an understanding of time, people, cultures
- An interesting track to take with you in the work in the future. Can we develop a place through sound?

Challenges:

- Time, knowledge, money
- Not part of the process today
- Lack of understanding of the benefits - what can they provide?
- Disturbance reports = costs
- Who should be satisfied?
- Difference/choice of sound art and sound design
- Knowledge: an opportunity, how, when, where, effects?
- Economy
- Complexity of laws etc., where/when/how
- Limited knowledge
- Time
- Time, technology, availability, priorities, money, premises
- Do several people see the same user benefit? "Value" versus "everything else"
- Limited processes
- Accessibility (for those with hearing impairments)
- Requires (in some cases) smartphone (inaccessible)
- Rights (music) require some work to use
- Ignorance
- Time pressure = de-prioritized
- Economics
- Human influence
- Requires knowledge in technology and computer programs
- Work with sound is very regulated
- Difficult when few will invest in sound in urban planning - tradition
- Technology can fail
- I guess that "sound" is usually treated as "noise", hence the silence goal
- Availability of composer/sound designer
- Lack of knowledge

- Rights (music)
- Capitalism
- The rapidness of the contemporary - gets dated
- Political situation that does not prioritize the unprofitable
- Finances for performers (composers, musicians, authors)
- Prejudice and everyone's various relationship to different sounds
- Technical: how sound is made available

3.2 Ideas and suggestions for micro project in connection to Flemingsberg development

The diversity of practitioners in attendance made this event a particularly interesting gathering of expertise and viewpoints, and our team put forward the invitation to the three small groups to do a small brainstorming session and draft a list of suggestions for micro projects which could be of potential interest for the development of Flemingsberg as a residential area in the future. A summary of the ideas shared is annotated here:

Group: 1 – Group rapporteur Marica

Visions - future

- Traffic noise is gone
- More nature sounds like bird sounds and insect sounds
- Sound is a natural part of urban planning
- Active quiet environments and sound design
- Sound and health, a new field of research
- Silence becomes important
- Sound art becomes available
- ASMR & white noise

Micro-collaborations and projects

- Develop soundwalks that are available (platsspecifika), collaboration Södertörn University, Huddinge municipality and the region of Stockholm. Create open WiFi in the municipality.
- Make short temporary projects in the municipality, such as sounds, live music, stories
- Collaboration culture and urban planning with students at SH and SMI, linked to existing projects
- Collaborate with Östragymnasiet, dialogue, upper secondary school work

Group: 2 Group rapporteur Alethe

Visions - future

- Listening to history: What did the 20th century sound like?
- Direct translation of languages
- Soundproofed homes
- Equal access to knowledge
- Equal access to technology
- It's hard to be an optimist.
- Designed sound environment
- Valued and caring mind
- El <> bullerfriare
- Easy to think unsatisfied, scary!
- Selectively and individually

- Hear other sounds "what does the tree say"

Micro-collaborations and projects

- The choreography – extend to all languages available
- Start collecting sound (Stockholm County Museum)
- Interacting hearing/deaf, learning to sing by feeling vibrations and sound waves
- Expand fossil-free areas
- Artist co-lab with KTH, MAX MSP-programming

Group 3: Group rapporteur Erik

Visions - future

- 2170 urban planning: interactive dialogue with citizens, collecting, communicating, sorting
- Interactive, AI, virtual environments
- More collective (again?)
- Century of hearing (including gaze)
- Sound museum

Micro-collaborations and projects

- Pilot project linked to an urban development project, cooperation between students and municipalities
- Sound artists in urban planning processes
- Sound inventory in different environments/eras
- Campus choir(s): orchestras, bands, ensembles, scenic poetry, etc.
- Continued collaboration with artists: sound art, performing arts (residence and the like)
- Soundwalks in a place for the public
- Available audio archives: museum? students?
- Let artists re-create a place with sound
- Variations on a theme: music for different sound environments

4. Concluding remarks and next steps

This event was an interesting opportunity for exchange of ideas and views from different profiles to include artists, researchers, the public and private sector, and contributes at refining our ongoing work centred on multimodal interaction in the context of participatory spatial planning done as part to WP3. Small group discussions were generative and led to ideas with potential for future exploration. In the PwY project we continue work on our hands-on activities and in the coming period further research will be done around this topic. For further updates on the work done and plans ahead welcome to follow us on our online platforms: <https://medium.com/youth-plan> visit our project

Acknowledgments

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